

APPLICATION OF THE AHP METHOD FOR SELECTING THE PROCEDURE FOR REMOVING POST-DETONATION REMNANTS OF EXPLOSIVES FROM THE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: *The subject and goal of this paper are focused on areas contaminated by military activities, as well as providing answers regarding the selection of the best way for removing explosive material (EM) residues from polluted areas using the AHP multi-criteria decision-making model. Military training grounds play a crucial role in the training and testing of weapons and ammunition, but they are also a significant source of environmental pollution. During military activities, explosive materials enter the environment through the activation of explosive ordnance (XO). This typically occurs due to weapon firing, unexploded XO remnants during detonation, improper storage, and destruction of XO. Explosive materials contaminate soil and groundwater and, through leaching, can further spread into other ecosystems.*

Keywords: MCDM, AHP method, environment, explosives.

1. INTRODUCTION

Military training and testing activities play a crucial role in national defense, but they also contribute to environmental contamination, particularly through the release of explosive materials into soil and groundwater. Explosives such as trinitrotoluene (TNT), cyclotrimethylenetrinitramine (RDX), and octogen (HMX) are widely used in military operations, yet their environmental persistence and toxicity raise significant concerns (Bernstein & Ronen, 2012). The contamination of military ranges occurs due to munitions activation, unexploded ordnance, improper disposal, and degradation of explosive residues, leading to long-term ecological effects (Brannon & Myers, 1997; Juhasz & Naidu, 2007).

The environmental fate of these explosives varies based on their chemical properties, soil composition, and biodegradation potential. Studies have shown that explosive residues can persist in terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, posing risks to human health and wildlife (Kalderis et al., 2011). Furthermore, improper remediation efforts may exacerbate contamination rather than eliminate it. Various remediation strategies, including chemical treatment, soil excavation, and biodegradation, have been proposed to address the problem (McGrath, 1995). A systematic approach using multi-criteria decision analysis has been introduced to determine optimal removal routes for RDX and HMX in contaminated sites (Bajić et al., 2024).

Given the widespread environmental hazards associated with explosives in military ranges, identifying efficient and sustainable remediation methods is imperative. This study employs the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) model to evaluate the effectiveness of various removal techniques, aiming to mitigate the impact of explosive contaminants and ensure ecosystem resilience (Brannon & Pennington, 2012). By integrating multi-criteria decision-making principles, this research seeks to provide actionable insights for environmental management and pollution mitigation in military training areas.

2. DEVELOPMENT OF MULTICRITERIA DECISION MODEL

The selection of appropriate environmental remediation technologies is fundamentally influenced by various site-specific factors, including geographic location, soil composition, water body characteristics, contaminant type and concentration, as well as local geological and climatic conditions. Additionally, remediation urgency indicators—such as proximity to residential areas, contaminant toxicity, and intended future land use—must be taken into account when planning a remediation project. Prior to implementing any

remediation measures, comprehensive site investigations and urgency assessments should be conducted. The gathered data is then reviewed by experts, who evaluate possible alternatives based on technical explanations and relevant recommendations. Typically, multiple remediation options are available, and determining the optimal approach requires a scientifically developed decision-making model based on suitable MCDM methods.

During expert evaluations, three primary criteria are used to assess the sustainability of recommended remediation strategies: economic, environmental, and technological impacts. Economic considerations include factors such as equipment costs, operational expenses, and costs associated with detection and analysis. Environmental factors encompass risks of secondary contamination, potential hazards to human health, and public acceptance of the remediation approach. The technological aspect is evaluated based on remediation efficiency, required implementation time, and the maturity of the technology (Li et al., 2018, Bajić et al., 2024). Detailed overview of the technological data relevant to explosives as environmental pollutants was given elsewhere (Bajić et al., 2024).

When determining the most effective remediation technology, factors beyond efficiency, technological maturity, and cost must be taken into account, including:

- Physicochemical characteristics of explosive materials
- Extent and intensity of soil and water contamination
- Geological and hydrogeological characteristics of the affected area
- Previous applications of remediation technologies in similar cases
- Simplicity of methods, accessibility, and feasibility of equipment usage
- Potential secondary environmental impacts and mitigation approaches
- Risks to human life and health
- Social acceptability of the remediation approach
- Economic, technical, and time constraints

In addressing complex and large-scale problems, professional experts from relevant fields are frequently consulted to analyze and discuss potential solutions. Their insights serve as valuable references in the decision-making process. However, treating all expert opinions equally without considering variations in expertise—such as quality, knowledge, experience, and ability—can lead to an imbalanced assessment. To ensure a more rational and scientifically grounded decision, it is essential to first carefully evaluate the relative weight of each expert’s input (Bajić et al., 2024).

3. RESULTS

The expert competency model was used to rank experts based on the criteria presented elsewhere (Bajić et al., 2024). Their ranks are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparison matrix of experts based on given criteria

Rank	Expert	Weight coefficient of each expert
1	E1	0.3038
2	E2	0.2830
3	E3, E5	0.1415
4	E4	0.1261

During the survey, the most optimal remediation technologies (alternatives) for the given case were proposed, and experts expressed their opinions using quantitative comparisons of criteria and alternatives within the designated software. The criteria included:

- Cost (C1)
- Remediation burden (C2)
- Remediation efficiency (C3)
- Operability (C4)
- Technology maturity (C5)

The proposed alternatives were:

- Photolysis (A1)
- Redox reactions (A2)
- Excavation (A3)

- Solidification (A4)
- Ultrasonication (A5)
- Incineration (A6)
- Thermal desorption (A7)

Final comparison matrices, based on the opinions of each expert, are presented in Tables 2 to 7.

Table 2: Criteria comparison matrix

Criteria	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
C1	1	2.6458	0.189	5	3
C2	0.378	1	0.126	1.291	0.2236
C3	5.2915	7.9373	1	7.4833	4.4721
C4	0.2	0.7746	0.1336	1	0.1543
C5	0.3333	4.4721	0.2236	6.4807	1

Table 3: Alternative comparison matrix for criterion C1

C1	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7
A1	1	5.9161	7.4833	1.2247	3.1623	1.5811	1.5811
A2	0.169	1	1.4142	1	1.1547	1.4142	0.4082
A3	0.1336	0.7071	1	0.2887	0.7746	0.866	0.866
A4	0.8165	1	3.4641	1	1	1.1547	0.866
A5	0.3162	0.866	1.291	1	1	1.2247	1
A6	0.6325	0.7071	1.1547	0.866	0.8165	1	0.3536
A7	0.6325	2.4495	1.1547	1.1547	1	2.8284	1

Table 4: Alternative comparison matrix for criterion C2

C2	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7
A1	1	1	6.4807	4.4721	1.1547	1.1547	1.2247
A2	1	1	4.2426	4.4721	0.2582	0.866	1
A3	0.1543	0.2357	1	0.25	0.2582	0.25	0.2236
A4	0.2236	0.2236	4	1	0.2	0.2582	0.2582
A5	0.866	3.873	3.873	5	1	4.4721	4
A6	0.866	1.1547	4	3.873	0.2236	1	0.4472
A7	0.8165	1	4.4721	3.873	0.25	2.2361	1

Table 5: Alternative comparison matrix for criterion C3

C3	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7
A1	1	4.899	2.6458	4.2426	4.5826	3.1623	3.1623
A2	0.2041	1	1.118	1	1.291	1.291	1.118
A3	0.378	0.8944	1	0.3162	0.9129	0.7746	0.4082
A4	0.2357	1	3.1623	1	1	0.3536	0.2887
A5	0.2182	0.7746	1.0954	1	1	1	1
A6	0.3162	0.7746	1.291	2.8284	1	1	0.4472
A7	0.3162	0.8944	2.4495	3.4641	1	2.2361	1

Table 6: Alternative comparison matrix for criterion C4

C4	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7
A1	1	3.873	4.5826	3.4641	2.4495	2.2361	2.2361
A2	0.2582	1	2.8284	2.2361	0.8165	2.4495	1.7321
A3	0.2182	0.3536	1	0.2887	0.5774	0.2887	0.2887
A4	0.2887	0.4472	3.4641	1	0.7746	2	0.5774
A5	0.4082	1.2247	1.7321	1.291	1	1.291	1.291
A6	0.4472	0.4082	3.4641	0.5	0.7746	1	0.4472
A7	0.4472	0.5774	3.4641	1.7321	0.7746	2.2361	1

Table 7: Alternative comparison matrix for criterion C5

7	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7
A1	1	1.4142	2.6458	3.1623	1.1547	1.7321	1.5811
A2	0.7071	1	4.2426	3.1623	1.291	2.4495	2.2361
A3	0.378	0.2357	1	0.3162	0.8165	0.3162	0.7071
A4	0.3162	0.3162	3.1623	1	2.2361	0.5774	0.5774
A5	0.866	0.7746	1.2247	0.4472	1	1.2247	1.118
A6	0.5774	0.4082	3.1623	1.7321	0.8165	1	0.5774
A7	0.6325	0.4472	1.4142	1.7321	0.8944	1.7321	1

Each comparison matrix of alternatives relative to a given criterion has been normalized, and the weighting coefficients of the alternatives concerning that criterion have been obtained. Based on the criterion comparison matrix, the weighting coefficients for the criteria were obtained (Figure 1), which, when multiplied with the alternative-criterion matrix, provide the final results of the model (Table 8 and Figure 2).

Figure 1: Graphical representation of the obtained values of the weighting coefficients for the criteria

Table 8: Alternative rankings

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	Result
A1	0.0635	0.0099	0.2011	0.0128	0.0332	0.3206
A2	0.0196	0.007	0.0583	0.0064	0.0358	0.127
A3	0.0144	0.0017	0.0418	0.0019	0.0094	0.0693
A4	0.0299	0.0026	0.0512	0.0043	0.0177	0.1058
A5	0.0219	0.017	0.0511	0.0053	0.0185	0.1139
A6	0.0194	0.0061	0.0607	0.0037	0.0185	0.1085
A7	0.0333	0.0076	0.0887	0.0056	0.0199	0.1551

Figure 2: Graphical representation of the alternative ranking

The application of the Analytic Hierarchy Process and the expert competency model led to the clear identification of A1 (photolysis) as the most suitable option for the remediation of EM from the contaminated sites. The application of the expert competency model proved to be appropriate and justified, despite encountering significant challenges—namely, the limited number of available experts and their insufficient experience with issues related to EM contamination, remediation pathways, and relevant techniques. These difficulties are largely due to the fact that the problem has not been clearly addressed in Serbia, and suitable remediation technologies are still not developed or widely implemented in the country. Although photolysis is not a new method, it has yet to be fully confirmed as a successful and widely viable solution. Nevertheless, it ranked highest due to its demonstrated benefits. Correspondingly, the consistency of the pairwise comparisons and the significant margin in priority weights among the alternatives indicate a stable decision outcome.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper describes a multi-criteria decision-making model based on the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) method. The model has been adapted and modified to minimize the possibility of errors when comparing criteria and alternatives. If errors occur, the model identifies them as outlier values and applies appropriate procedures to correct them.

In addition to the multi-criteria decision-making model, an expert competency model has been integrated. This competency model ranks the "weight" (importance) of experts based on specific criteria. These criteria are established by decision-makers and, in this case, pertain to the academic and professional development and performance of experts.

The application of the modified AHP model in the remediation of explosive materials has resulted in the selection of the best remediation technology—photolysis—based on the overall expert consensus. The model has demonstrated its effectiveness in environmental remediation and can also be applied in other fields such as transportation, market analysis, human resources, and more.

Future development of the multi-criteria decision-making model should be accompanied by the implementation of new mathematical models, leveraging its application for decision-making processes that require complex analysis.

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LITERATURE

- Bajić, Z., Bogdanov, J., & Vujković, B. (2024). The development of a multi-criteria model for the best removal route of post-detonation RDX and HMX explosive remnants in the environment. *SYMOPIS 2024*.
- Bernstein, A., & Ronen, Z. (2012). Biodegradation of the explosives TNT, RDX, and HMX. In *Microbial degradation of xenobiotics* (pp. 135-176). Springer.
- Brannon, J. M., & Pennington, J. C. (2012). Environmental fate and transport process descriptors for explosives. *ERDC/EL TR-02-10*. U.S. Army Engineer Research and Development Center.
- Brannon, M., & Myers, T. E. (1997). Review of fate and transport processes of explosives. *Technical Report IRRP-97-2*. U.S. Army Corps of Engineers.
- Juhasz, A. L., & Naidu, R. (2007). Explosives: Fate, dynamics, and ecological impact in terrestrial and marine environments. *Reviews of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, 191, 163-215.
- Kalderis, D., Juhasz, A. L., Boopathy, R., & Comfort, S. (2011). Soils contaminated with explosives: Environmental fate and evaluation of state-of-the-art remediation processes (IUPAC Technical Report). *Pure and Applied Chemistry*, 83(7), 1407-1484.
- Li, X., Li, J., Sui, H., He, L., Cao, X., & Li, Y. (2018). Evaluation and determination of soil remediation schemes using a modified AHP model and its application in a contaminated coking plant. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 353, 300-311.
- McGrath, C. J. (1995). *Technical Report IRRP-95-2*. U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, Waterways.
- Veličković, Z., Bajić, Z., Karkalić, R., Ivanković, N., Gigović, Lj., Kričak, Đ., Vuruna, M. (2016). Uticaj vojnih aktivnosti na zagađenje zemljišta poligona „Pasuljanske livade“, *Energija, ekonomija, ekologija*, No. 1-2, 148–154.